

Figure S1: ^{23}Na Imaging (* Bottles with aqueous saline solution as reference) A Image Plane alignment B Anatomical imaging C Water imaging D Sodium imaging with ROI marking: 1) background noise 2) Bottles with aqueous saline solution 3) posterior skin 4) the center of muscle tissue 5) tibial bone marrow 6) subcutaneous fat tissue E Example of ^{23}Na -imaging in non-genetic obesity F Example of ^{23}Na -imaging in POMC

Figure S2: Correlation between Na⁺ and water content of all enrolled patients in different compartments: A triceps surae muscle; B skin; C tibia bone; D subcutaneous fat.